

**STAFF DEVELOPMENT AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIBRARIANS IN
CROSS RIVER UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY (CRUTECH)
LIBRARY CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA**

By

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study was to determine staff development and productivity in Cross River University of Technology (CRUTECH) Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, four null hypotheses were generated to direct the study.. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. A sample of one hundred and five (105) respondents was randomly selected for the study. The staff development and productivity questionnaire (SDPQ) was the main instrument used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to both face validation by the supervisor and experts in measurement and evaluation in the Faculty of Education, University of Calabar.. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis was the statistical analysis technique adopted to test the hypotheses. The results of the analysis revealed that, in-service training, conference attendance, seminar attendance and workshop attendance significantly relate with staff productivity (in terms of cataloguing, citation, referencing and shelving). Based on the findings of the study it was recommended that in-service training should be introduced in all divisions of the library to increase staff productivity.

Key Words: Staff Development, Productivity, Librarians, CRUTECH Library, Nigeria